

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

JUSTIFICATION OF SOME APPROACHES TO THE ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

The article presents a different approach to the theoretical foundations of the method for constructing numerical solutions of second-order linear differential equations with variable coefficients. In the process of solving second-order differential equations with variable coefficients, the absolute convergence of successive approximations to a given function in a given set was studied. It is shown that the corresponding limit in this approximation is a solution of the given differential equation. When solving linear differential equations with variable coefficients using the method of undetermined coefficients, a general expression was found for the coefficients of a functional series, which facilitated the finding of a system of linearly independent fundamental solutions of the equation.

A comparative analysis of numerical and quadrature solutions of differential equations is also presented. In the problem under consideration, the results obtained from an approximate solution of a given differential equation using the Euler and Runge-Kutta methods were compared with the results obtained from an exact solution of this equation. At each precisely chosen step, the intersection points of the lines and the angular coefficients of the tangents drawn to the integral curve at these points were found.

Keywords. Picard approach, uniform convergence, numerical method, successive approximation, Leonard Euler and Runge-Kutta method, increment ratio.

Introduction

A comparative analysis of the obtained values is necessary to select the most accurate and effective of the approximate or numerical methods for solving differential equations for which exact solutions cannot be found. The theorem of existence of a solution can also be proved by other methods with general assumptions [1]. Thus, for the existence of a solution, the only condition that can be imposed is the continuity of the function $f(x, y)$ in both arguments x and y . If no additional conditions are imposed on the function $f(x, y)$, then the initial condition $y(x_0) = y_0$ does not determine only one solution, that is, there is no need for a uniqueness theorem [2]. If we impose only the continuity condition of the function $f(x, y)$ in both arguments x and y the differential equation $y' = f(x, y)$, then we can prove that there exists at least one solution satisfying the initial condition $(x_0) = y_0$.

For this purpose, 1) the existence of a solution is proved by the method of successive approximations used to integrate the given first-order differential equations, provided that the Lipschitz condition is satisfied with respect to the variable y function $f(x, y)$; 2) general expressions for the coefficients of functional series were found when solving linear differential equations with variable coefficients using the method of undetermined coefficients; 3) the results obtained using approximate calculation methods of Leonard Euler, Runge-Kutta and the exact solution of this equation were compared.

Problem Statement and Research

The theorem on the existence and uniqueness of solutions to differential equations has a large number of expressions and proof methods. To prove this theorem, we first prove Picard's theorem.

Here it is assumed that the function $f(x, y)$ on the right-hand side of equation

$$y' = f(x, y) \quad (1)$$

satisfies the initial conditions

$$y(x_0) = y_0 \quad (2)$$

Picard's theorem proves that the function $f(x, y)$ on the right-hand side of equation (1) is continuous inside a certain rectangle and satisfies the Lipschitz condition with respect to y . For the existence of a solution it is sufficient that the function $f(x, y)$ be continuous, and proof of the existence of a solution using Peano's theorem is possible even if the function $f(x, y)$ does not satisfy the Lipschitz condition in y . In general, theorems on the existence of solutions are not constructive [3]. Since these theorems do not show how to establish the existence of a solution, they only show the existence of a solution to the equation and the fulfillment of other conditions, its uniqueness and continuous dependence on the right-hand side of the equation. Consequently, both in the equations of mathematical physics and in solving partial differential equations, this theorem does not allow one to construct a solution. However, Picard's theorem provides such a possibility and can provide a constructive method for constructing a solution [4].

Picard's Theorem. Suppose that the function $f(x, y)$ is discontinuous in any rectangle Π and satisfies the Lipschitz condition. That is, $f(x, y) \in C(\Pi) \cap Lip_y(\Pi)$. Here, the rectangle Π is defined as follows

$$\Pi = \{ (x, y) ; |x - x_0| \leq a, |y - y_0| \leq b \}$$

Then problem (1), (2) has a solution in the interval $[x_0 - h, x_0 + h]$ and this solution is unique. Here $h = \min\left(a, \frac{b}{M}, \frac{1}{L}\right)$, $M = \sup_{\Pi} |f(x, y)|$, L is the Lipschitz constant, that is, if for

$$\exists L > 0, \forall (x, y'), (x, y'') \in \Pi$$

condition is satisfied

$$|f(x, y') - f(x, y'')| < L|y' - y''| \text{ that } f \in Lip_y(\Pi)$$

In the formulation of the problem for this theorem, unlike other theorems, it is assumed that when proving the existence and uniqueness of a solution, only the fulfillment of the condition is used $f(x, y) \in C(\Pi) \cap Lip_y(\Pi)$. These conditions simplify the proof of the theorem, allowing one to prove the existence and uniqueness of the solution by the approximation method (Picard's method) [5]. In classical literature, the proof of Picard's theorem is given by proving a lemma on integral equations [6].

Lemma. A function $y(x)$ is a solution to problem (1), (2) if and only if this function is a solution to the integral equation

$$y = y_0 + \int_{x_0}^x f(s, y(s)) ds \tag{3}$$

The proof of this lemma implies that instead of proving the existence and uniqueness of a solution to the Cauchy problem, one should consider the existence and uniqueness of the integral equation [7]. That is, it is sufficient to prove the existence of a continuous function satisfying the integral equation (3). To do this, we'll use the method of successive approximations. Here, we'll primarily consider a rectangle Π centered at the point (x_0, y_0) and take into account that in the segment $[x_0 - a, x_0 + a]$ there is such a segment $[x_0 - h, x_0 + h]$ in which the function $f(x, y)$ is continuous in y and satisfies the Lipschitz condition. It can be proven that this segment contains a solution to the Cauchy problem, or that this solution extends beyond the given segment [8]. Depending on the constant $h = \min\left(a, \frac{b}{M}, \frac{1}{L}\right)$ of existence of the solution outside the segment, either the existence and uniqueness of this solution can continue, or the existence and uniqueness of this solution can be violated.

This article addresses three main problems:

Problem 1. A different approach to the theoretical foundations of the method for constructing numerical solutions of second-order linear differential equations with variable coefficients is presented. Along with various formulations of the mentioned theorems and statements, their application to the solution of second-order differential equations with variable coefficients is given. In the process of solving differential equations of this type, the uniform convergence of successive approximations to a given function in a given set was studied, and it was shown that the corresponding limit in this approximation is a solution to the given differential equation.

It is known that for a differential equation of n order

$$y^{(n)} = f(x, y, y', y'', \dots, y^{(n-1)}) \tag{5}$$

the Cauchy problem satisfying the initial conditions $y^{(k)}(x_0) = y_0^{(k)}$, $(k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n - 1)$ is carried out to a system of equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y' &= y_1, \\ y_1' &= y_2, \\ &\dots\dots\dots \\ y^{(n)} &= f(x, y, y_1, \dots, y_{n-1}) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{6}$$

Therefore, the methods developed for approximate integration of systems of differential equations are also applicable to equation (5) [9]. However, general schemes for the approximate solution of differential systems without taking into account the specific properties of system (6) are unnecessarily complex. For numerical integration of differential equation (5) it is advisable to use special formulas. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider the solution of the Cauchy problem, a second-order differential equation

$$y'' = f(x, y, y') \tag{7}$$

satisfying the initial conditions

$$y(x_0) = y_0, y'(x_0) = y'_0 \tag{8}$$

from the point of view of relevance. By differentiating both sides of this equation with respect to its argument x , the values $y'''(x_0), y^{IV}(x_0), \dots, y^{(n)}(x_0)$ of its derivatives $y''', y^{IV}, \dots, y^{(n)}$ that satisfy the initial conditions (8) are found

$$y'' = f(x, y, y')|_{x=x_0, y=y_0, y'=y'_0} = f(x_0, y_0, y'_0) = y''(x_0)$$

Let us differentiate the last expression to the n order:

$$y''' = f'_x(x, y, y') + f'_y(x, y, y')y' + f'_{y'}(x, y, y')y''$$

$$y^{(n)} = f_x^{(n-2)}(x, y, y') + f_y^{(n-2)}(x, y, y')y^{(n-2)} + f_{y'}^{(n-2)}(x, y, y')y^{(n-1)}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} y''|_{x=x_0} &= f(x, y, y')|_{x=x_0} = y'' \\ y'''|_{x=x_0} &= f'(x, y, y')|_{x=x_0} = y''' \\ \dots\dots\dots \\ y^{(n)}|_{x=x_0} &= f^{(n-2)}(x, y, y')|_{x=x_0} = y_0^{(n-2)} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the values $y'''(x_0), y^{IV}(x_0), \dots, y^{(n)}(x_0)$ of higher-order derivatives $y''', y^{IV}, \dots, y^{(n)}$ into the Taylor series

$$y(x) = y(x_0) + \frac{y'(x_0)}{1!}(x - x_0) + \frac{y''(x_0)}{2!}(x - x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{y^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x - x_0)^n + \dots \quad (9)$$

a numerical solution of equation (7) was obtained that satisfies the initial conditions (8). The numerical error of the solution of the second-order differential equation (7) is measured directly by the error of the limit of the remainder of the Taylor formula [10].

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} R_n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{y^{(n+1)}(c)}{(n+1)!} (x - x_0)^{n+1} = 0, \quad c = x_0 + \theta(x - x_0), \quad 0 < \theta < 1$$

The solution of equation (7) converges on the interval $|x - x_0| < h \Rightarrow x_0 - h < x < x_0 + h$.

This means that the existence and uniqueness of the solution $y(x)$ near the point $x = x_0$ are proven.

Problem 2. Linear differential equations with variable coefficients

$$y'' + p(x)y' + q(x)y = 0 \quad (10)$$

satisfying the initial conditions (if the initial conditions for $x = x_0$ are given, they are reduced to conditions (10) by substituting $x - x_0 = t$)

$$y(0) = y_0, \quad y'(0) = y'_0 \quad (11)$$

the general expression for the coefficients of the functional series in the solution can be found using the method of undetermined coefficients [11]. In a second-order linear homogeneous equation with variable coefficients

$$y'' + p(x)y' + q(x)y = 0$$

flat $p(x) = x^k, q(x) = x$, finding a solution

$$y(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + a_3 x^3 + \dots + a_n x^n + \dots \quad (12)$$

depends on whether this sequence is convergent in the given domain. If the function defined by (12) is a solution of the equation

$$y'' + x^k y' + xy = 0 \quad (10^*)$$

then this function and its derivatives must turn into its identity.

Thus, when

$$y' = [\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n]' = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a_n x^{n-1} \quad \text{and} \quad y'' = [\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a_n x^{n-1}]' = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n(n-1) a_n x^{n-2}$$

we get

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n(n-1) a_n x^{n-2} + x^k \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a_n x^{n-1} + x \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n = 0$$

or

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n(n-1) a_n x^{n-2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a_n x^{n+k-1} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^{n+1} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The degree of the variable x can be reduced to the same value by making the appropriate substitutions in each of the sums of the last expression. In this case, a general expression for the coefficients of the power series (12) can be found. By substituting into the first sum $n - 2 = m$, the second sum $n + k - 1 = m$ and the third sum $n + 1 = m$ of equation (13), the coefficients a_n can be determined using the method of undetermined coefficients.

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (m+1)(m+2) a_{m+2} x^m + \sum_{m=k}^{\infty} (m-k+1) a_{m-k+1} x^m + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} a_{m-1} x^m = 0 \\ & 2a_2 + 2 \cdot 3a_3 x + 3 \cdot 4a_4 x^2 + \dots + (k-2)(k-1) a_{k-1} x^{k-3} + a_0 x + a_1 x^2 + \dots + a_{k-1} x^{k-1} + \\ & + \sum_{m=k}^{\infty} [(m+1)(m+2) a_{m+2} + (m-k+1) a_{m-k+1} + a_{m-1}] \cdot x^m = 0 \\ & 2a_2 + (2 \cdot 3a_3 + a_0) x + (3 \cdot 4a_4 + a_1) x^2 + \dots + (k-2)(k-1) a_{k-1} x^{k-3} + a_{k-1} x^{k-1} + \\ & + \sum_{m=k}^{\infty} [(m+1)(m+2) a_{m+2} + (m-k+1) a_{m-k+1} + a_{m-1}] \cdot x^m = 0 \end{aligned}$$

From this it is clear that along with $(k-1)$ the number of coefficients of the variables $x^0, x^1, x^2, \dots, x^{k-1}$ the coefficients of the variable x^m are also equal to zero, that is

$$\begin{aligned} & (m+1)(m+2) a_{m+2} + (m-k+1) a_{m-k+1} + a_{m-1} = 0 \\ & a_{m+2} = -\frac{(m-k+1) a_{m-k+1} + a_{m-1}}{(m+1)(m+2)} \end{aligned}$$

Let's find the coefficients a_n , starting with the k term (11*). Here, two criteria are taken into account, namely: $a_0 = 0, a_1 = 1$ and $a_0 = 1, a_1 = 0$.

1) $a_0 = 0, a_1 = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} m = k, a_{k+2} &= -\frac{a_1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = -\frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} \\ m = k+1, a_{k+3} &= -\frac{2a_2 - a_k}{(k+2)(k+3)} = -\frac{0}{(k+2)(k+3)} = 0 \\ m = k+2, a_{k+4} &= -\frac{3a_3 - a_{k+1}}{(k+3)(k+4)} = -\frac{1}{(k+3)(k+4)} \\ m = k+3, a_{k+5} &= -\frac{4a_4 - a_{k+2}}{(k+4)(k+5)} = -\frac{1}{(k+4)(k+5)} \cdot \frac{3}{(k+1)(k+2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$y_1(x) = -\frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} \cdot x^{k+2} + \frac{1}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+4} - \frac{1}{(k+4)(k+5)} \cdot \frac{3}{(k+1)(k+2)} \cdot x^{k+5} + \dots$$

$$2) a_0 = 1, \quad a_1 = 0.$$

$$m = k, a_{k+2} = -\frac{a_1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = -\frac{0}{(k+1)(k+2)} = 0$$

$$m = k+1, a_{k+3} = -\frac{2a_2 - a_k}{(k+2)(k+3)} = -\frac{0}{(k+2)(k+3)} = 0$$

$$m = k+2, a_{k+4} = -\frac{3a_3 - a_{k+1}}{(k+3)(k+4)} = \frac{2}{(k+3)(k+4)}$$

$$m = k+3, a_{k+5} = -\frac{4a_4 - a_{k+2}}{(k+4)(k+5)} = \frac{3}{(k+4)(k+5)}$$

$$y_2(x) = -\frac{2}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+4} + \frac{3}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+5} + \dots$$

Thus, since the general solution $y(x) = C_1 y_1(x) + C_2 y_2(x)$ of equation (11*) is

$$y(x) = C_1 \left[-\frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} \cdot x^{k+2} + \frac{1}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+4} - \frac{1}{(k+4)(k+5)} \cdot \frac{3}{(k+1)(k+2)} \cdot x^{k+5} + \dots \right] + C_2 \left[-\frac{2}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+4} + \frac{3}{(k+3)(k+4)} \cdot x^{k+5} + \dots \right]$$

Problem 3. For this purpose, the results obtained by applying the approximate calculation methods of Leonhard Euler and Runge-Kutta were compared with the exact solution of the given first-order differential equation. If it is required to find a solution satisfying the initial conditions (2) in a segment $[x_0, b]$ of a first-order differential equation (1) using an approximate method, then the solution of the differential equation $y(x)$ is found as the limit of a certain sequence $\{y_n(x)\}$ expressed by elementary functions or their integrals, and for sufficiently large numbers n the function $y_n(x)$ is an approximate value of the solution $y(x) \approx y_n(x)$.

In this case, the solution is presented in tabular form.

For a function $f(x, y)$ defined in any domain σ and taking finite values at all its points, the slope of the tangent $k = \operatorname{tg} \alpha = f(x, y)$ drawn to the curve at each point $(x, y) \in \sigma$ of the integral curve of the first-order differential equation (1) is equal to y' or $f(x, y)$. In this regard, by considering the tangent to a sufficiently small section of the integral curve as constant, this continuous curve $y = \phi(x)$ can be replaced by a broken line. Ultimately, this leads to finding an integral curve $y = y(x)$ satisfying the initial condition (2) for a first-order differential equation continuous on the right-hand side $f(x, y)$. It is known that the geometric solution of a differential equation means finding a curve such that the direction of the tangent to this curve at any point of this curve coincides with the direction field at the corresponding point. The basic principle of Euler's numerical method for integrating differential equations is to replace the derivative in a given differential equation with a ratio of increments [12].

Let us

$$y_k = y(x_k), \Delta y_k = y_{k+1} - y_k, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

$$\frac{\Delta y_k}{\Delta x} = f(x_k, y_k), \frac{y_{k+1} - y_k}{\Delta x} = f(x_k, y_k) \text{ or } \frac{y(x_{k+1}) - y(x_k)}{x_{k+1} - x_k} = f(x_k, y_k)$$

We will choose the calculation step $h = \frac{b-x_0}{n}$ and the division condition

$$x_0 = a < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_n = b$$

Let's divide the segment $[x_0, b]$ into equal n parts

$$x_0, x_1 = x_0 + h, x_2 = x_0 + 2h, \dots, x_{n-1} = x_0 + (n-1)h, x_n = x_0 + nh = b$$

points and find approximate values [2]:

$$\frac{y(x_{k+1}) - y(x_k)}{h} = f(x_k, y_k), y_{k+1} = y_k + f(x_k, y_k)h,$$

$$y_1 = y_0 + f(x_0, y_0)h, y_2 = y_1 + f(x_1, y_1)h, \dots, y_n = y_{n-1} + f(x_{n-1}, y_{n-1})h.$$

Based on the Euler method, initial conditions $y(1) = 0,5$ were specified and approximate values y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{10} of this differential equation were found from the distribution $x \in [1; 10]$, $n = 10$.

$$y' = \frac{y}{x} (1 + \ln y - \ln x) \quad (4)$$

$$y_1 = y_0 + f(x_0, y_0)h = y_0 + \frac{y_0}{x_0} \left(1 + \ln \frac{y_0}{x_0}\right) \cdot h = 0,5 + \frac{0,5}{1} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,5}{1}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,6381$$

$$y_2 = y_1 + f(x_1, y_1)h = 0,6381 + \frac{0,6381}{1,9} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,6381}{1,9}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,6110$$

$$y_3 = y_2 + f(x_2, y_2) \cdot h = 0,6110 + \frac{0,6110}{2,8} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,6110}{2,8}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,5079$$

$$y_4 = y_3 + f(x_3, y_3) \cdot h = 0,5079 + \frac{0,5079}{3,7} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,5079}{3,7}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,3861$$

$$y_5 = y_4 + f(x_4, y_4) \cdot h = 0,3861 + \frac{0,3861}{4,6} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,3861}{4,6}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,2745$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_6 &= y_5 + f(x_5, y_5) \cdot h = 0,2745 + \frac{0,2745}{5,5} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,2745}{5,5}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,1848 \\
y_7 &= y_6 + f(x_6, y_6) \cdot h = 0,1848 + \frac{0,1848}{6,4} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,1848}{6,4}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,1186 \\
y_8 &= y_7 + f(x_7, y_7) \cdot h = 0,1186 + \frac{0,1186}{7,3} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,1186}{7,3}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,0730 \\
y_9 &= y_8 + f(x_8, y_8) \cdot h = 0,0730 + \frac{0,0730}{8,2} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,0730}{8,2}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,0432 \\
y_{10} &= y_9 + f(x_9, y_9) \cdot h = 0,0432 + \frac{0,0432}{9,1} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,0432}{9,1}\right) \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,0246
\end{aligned}$$

The values calculated using the Euler numerical method

$$y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7, y_8, y_9, y_{10}$$

are given in the table.

Euler's method is important for its clarity and simple geometric meaning. The Euler polygonal line diagram is a Runge-Kutta diagram with first-order accuracy. To find approximate values using the Runge-Kutta scheme y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{10} , first calculate the increment of the function Δy and the approximate value y_1 using the following method:

$$\begin{aligned}
k_1 &= f(x_0, y_0) \cdot h, k_2 = f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_1}{2}\right) \cdot h, \\
k_3 &= f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_2}{2}\right) \cdot h, k_4 = f(x_0 + h; y_0 + k_3) \cdot h, \\
\Delta y &= \frac{1}{6}(k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4) \cdot h, y_1 \approx y_0 + \Delta y.
\end{aligned}$$

The given approximate values y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{10} of the differential equation (4) were calculated using the Runge-Kutta method. The calculations were carried out on the basis of the initial conditions $y(1) = 0,5$ and division of the segment $x \in [1; 10]$, $n = 10$. First, using the Runge-Kutta scheme, the numbers k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4 of a given first-order differential equation are found in the specified order, and with their help, approximate values y_2, \dots, y_{10} are found.

$$\begin{aligned}
k_1 &= f(x_0, y_0) \cdot h = \left[\frac{y_0}{x_0} \left(1 + \ln \frac{y_0}{x_0}\right)\right] \cdot h = [0,5(1 + \ln 0,5)] \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,1381 \\
k_2 &= f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_1}{2}\right) \cdot h = f\left(1 + \frac{0,9}{2}; 0,5 + \frac{0,1381}{2}\right) \cdot 0,9 = \\
&= [0,3924 \cdot (1 + \ln 0,3924)] \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,0228 \\
k_3 &= f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_2}{2}\right) \cdot h = f\left(1,45; 0,5 + \frac{0,0228}{2}\right) \cdot 0,9 = \\
&= [0,3527(1 + \ln 0,3527)] \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,0134 \\
k_4 &= f(x_0 + h; y_0 + k_3) \cdot h = f(1 + 0,9; 0,5 - 0,0134) \cdot 0,9 = \\
&= f(1,9; 0,4866) \cdot 0,9 = [0,2561 \cdot (1 + \ln 0,2561)] \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,0835 \\
\Delta y &= \left[\frac{1}{6}(0,1381 + 0,0457 - 0,0268 - 0,0835)\right] \cdot 0,9 \approx 0,0122 \\
y_1 &\approx y_0 + \Delta y = 0,5 + 0,0122 = 0,5122 \\
y_1 &= 0,5122, x_1 = x_0 + h = 1,9 \\
k_1 &= f(x_1, y_1) \cdot h = \frac{y_1}{x_1} \left(1 + \ln \frac{y_1}{x_1}\right) \cdot h = \left[\frac{0,5122}{1,9} \left(1 + \ln \frac{0,5122}{1,9}\right)\right] \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,0754 \\
k_2 &= f\left(x_1 + \frac{h}{2}; y_1 + \frac{k_1}{2}\right) \cdot h = f(2,35; 0,4746) \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,1090 \\
k_3 &= f\left(x_1 + \frac{h}{2}; y_1 + \frac{k_2}{2}\right) \cdot h = f(2,35; 0,4578) \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,1115 \\
k_4 &= f(x_1 + h; y_1 + k_3) \cdot h = f(1,9 + 0,9; 0,5123 - 0,1115) \cdot 0,9 = \\
&= f(2,8; 0,4008) \cdot 0,9 \approx -0,1216 \\
\Delta y &= \left[\frac{1}{6}(k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4)\right] \cdot h \approx -0,1062 \\
y_2 &\approx y_1 + \Delta y = 0,5123 - 0,1062 = 0,4060
\end{aligned}$$

Based on the conditions of this problem, calculations proceed as follows.

Calculating values y_3, \dots, y_{10} using this scheme and in the specified sequence, first the numbers k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4 are calculated and the corresponding increment of the function Δy is determined, then approximate values y_k ($k = \overline{3,10}$) are found:

$$0,2884, 0,1925, 0,1216, 0,0759, 0,0464, 0,0279, 0,0166, 0,0098.$$

These schemes are distinguished by their diversity. The Runge-Kutta method is important for the high-precision numerical solution of differential equations. As the Runge-Kutta method's dimensional order increases, the problem becomes more complex, while the accuracy, albeit slightly, improves. Thus, all widely used high-order methods (for example, fifth-order) can achieve an accuracy improvement of a part in a thousand.

Therefore, when using numerical methods, it is always advisable to choose between dividing a given segment into smaller parts using a simple method or calculating the function at the division points of this segment using

more complex methods [13]. A certain portion of the given segments should be divided in such a way that these division points produce a more accurate result. This usually depends on the formulation of the given problem. Therefore, the Runge-Kutta method of a higher order than the fourth is not used very often, and from the entire family of divisions, only the fourth-order method is used. To compare the approximate results with the exact solution, an exact solution of this differential equation was found. Thus, the general and particular solutions of problem (1), (2), that is the solution of the differential equation

$$y' = \frac{y}{x}(1 + \ln y - \ln x)$$

by the quadrature method, satisfying the initial condition $y(1) = 0,5$ has the form:

$$y' = \frac{y}{x} \left(1 + \ln \frac{y}{x}\right), dy = \frac{y}{x} \left(1 + \ln \frac{y}{x}\right) dx, \frac{y}{x} = t, y = tx, dy = tdx + xdt, tdx + xdt = t(1 + \ln t)dx, \\ xdt = t \ln t dx, \int \frac{dt}{t \ln t} = \int \frac{dx}{x}, \\ \ln |\ln t| = \ln |x| + \ln c, \ln t = xc, t = e^{xc}$$

Thus, $y = xe^{xc}$ the general solution of a given differential equation $y = xe^{x \ln 0,5}$ is a particular solution satisfying the initial condition $y(1) = 0,5$. Here $0,5 = 1 \cdot e^c, c = \ln 0,5 \approx -0,69315$. As a result, the appropriate values, taking into account the division of the segment $x \in [1; 10]$, $n = 10, h = \frac{10-1}{10} = 0,9$ are calculated $y_0 = y(x_0) = 0,5$ and compared.

$$y_1 = 1,9e^{-0,6932 \cdot 1,9} \approx 0,5091, y_2 = 2,8e^{-0,6932 \cdot 2,8} \approx 0,4020, \\ y_3 = 3,7e^{-0,6932 \cdot 3,7} \approx 0,2847, y_4 = 4,6e^{-0,6932 \cdot 4,6} \approx 0,1897 \\ y_5 = 5,5e^{-0,6932 \cdot 5,5} \approx 0,1215, y_6 = 6,4e^{-0,69315 \cdot 6,4} \approx 0,075786, \\ y_7 = 7,3e^{-0,6932 \cdot 7,3} \approx 0,0463, y_8 = 8,2e^{-0,6932 \cdot 8,2} \approx 0,0279, \\ y_9 = 9,1e^{-0,6932 \cdot 9,1} \approx 0,0166, y_{10} = 10e^{-0,6932 \cdot 10} \approx 0,0098$$

The calculated values $y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7, y_8, y_9, y_{10}$ are presented in the table.

Table.

Values $y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7, y_8, y_9, y_{10}$ calculated using by quadrature, Euler's and Runge-Kutta method

N	x_k	y_k	$y_k(E)$	$y_k(R - K)$
0	1	0,5	0,5	0,5
1	1,9	0,5091	0,6381	0,5122
2	2,8	0,4020	0,6110	0,4060
3	3,7	0,2847	0,5079	0,2884
4	4,6	0,1897	0,3861	0,1925
5	5,5	0,121534	0,2745	0,1216
6	6,4	0,075786	0,1848	0,0759
7	7,3	0,0463	0,1186	0,0464
8	8,2	0,0279	0,0730	0,0279
9	9,1	0,0166	0,0432	0,0166
10	10	0,0098	0,0246	0,0098

It is known that the solution of a differential equation geometrically means finding a curve such that the direction of the tangent at any point of this curve coincides with the direction of the field at the corresponding point. Let us construct an approximate solution, subject to the condition of tangency $k = tg \alpha = f(x, y)$ to the curve at each point $M(x, y)$ of the integral curve (fig.1). Considering that the tangent to the integral curve at the point $M_0 = M(x_0, y_0)$ has an angular coefficient $k_1 = f(x_0, y_0)$, as well as the intersection point of the lines $y - y_0 = k_1(x - x_0)$ and $x = x_0 + \frac{h}{2}$, that is, we find the point $N_1 \left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_1}{2}\right)$. Since the tangent $k_2 = f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_1}{2}\right)$ to the integral curve at this point N_1 is equal to the slope of the line $x = x_0 + \frac{h}{2}$, we draw a line $M(x_0, y_0)$ from the point to the intersection point with the line $y - y_0 = k_2(x - x_0)$ and find the point $N_2 \left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_2}{2}\right)$. The tangent to the integral curve $k_3 = f\left(x_0 + \frac{h}{2}; y_0 + \frac{k_2}{2}\right)$ at this point N_2 will be equal to the slope of the line. So, let's draw a straight line $x = x_0 + h$ with the angle coefficient k_3 from the point $M(x_0, y_0)$ to the point of intersection with the line $y - y_0 = k_3(x - x_0)$ and find the point $N_3(x_0 + h; y_0 + k_3)$. Let's find the coefficient of the angle of the tangent $k_4 = f(x_0 + h; y_0 + k_3)$ to the curve at point N_3 .

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